

30 Abstract

31 The emerging reductive catalytic fractionation biorefinery which is currently under development aims to convert
32 woody biomass efficiently into high-value products. Despite its potential, the environmental consequences of its
33 implementation are not well known. Therefore, a forward-looking consequential life cycle assessment examines
34 greenhouse gas emissions associated with its products (pulp, phenolic monomers, and oligomers) compared to
35 alternative market options. Findings indicate that current greenhouse gas emissions exceed those of the existing
36 alternatives, with by-products and the gaseous waste stream as major contributors. Process adaptation to (i) produce
37 higher-valued products (bleached pulps, phenols, and propylene) and (ii) incinerate gaseous waste stream for
38 energy are proposed, potentially reducing emissions by up to 50%, outperforming alternative options. Compared
39 to land-based transportation, waterways can increase feedstock availability by up to 1000 km without an increase
40 in emissions. In conclusion, the consequential approach provides valuable insights for enhancing and optimizing
41 the environmental performance of the process.

42

43 **Keywords:** Carbon footprint, bio-economy, biomass, reductive catalytic fractionation, renewable carbon, wood
44 value chain.

45 1 Introduction

46 The 21st century presents significant global challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity decline, and the
47 growing global demand for energy and rare materials (Müller et al., 2015). These challenges have led to the
48 crossing of six of the nine planetary boundaries, as demonstrated by the severe consequences they have had
49 (Richardson et al., 2023). To address these challenges, the European Union advocates for the establishment of a
50 European bioeconomy (Söderholm and Lundmark, 2009). In 2018, the European Commission introduced the
51 Sustainable European Bioeconomy Strategy, which aims to tackle these challenges, including the substitution of
52 fossil-based products with renewable feedstocks (European Commission, 2018).

53 One of the key components of the European strategy is the utilization of lignocellulosic biomass, such as wood,
54 to produce sustainable materials, fuels, and chemicals (European Commission, 2018; Van Meerbeek et al., 2019).
55 However, currently, only 5% of the lignocellulosic feedstock is utilized for high-value applications. One of the
56 primary reasons for this limited usage is the recalcitrance of lignin, which refers to its resistance to undergo
57 chemical reactions (Calvaruso et al., 2017).

58 Recently, considerable efforts have been devoted to tackling the challenge of lignin recalcitrance by developing
59 innovative biorefineries to unfold the full potential of the lignocellulosic feedstock by valorizing pulp and more
60 specifically, lignin into high-value chemicals (Budzinski and Nitzsche, 2016; Jiang et al., 2021), materials
61 (Balakshin et al., 2020), and fuels (Bond et al., 2014; Cheali et al., 2016). Schutyser et al. (2015) introduced the
62 reductive catalytic fractionation (RCF) process, a lignin-first technology valorizing both polysaccharides,
63 contained in the pulp, and lignin components into a handful of chemicals reaching a carbon conversion rate of
64 78% of the initial biomass (Liao et al., 2020; Schutyser et al., 2018; Van den Bosch et al., 2015). Given this
65 technological potential, the present study focuses on the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of RCF technology.

66 Life cycle assessment (LCA) studies on the '*lignin-first*' technologies show that wood-based products have
67 significantly lower GHG emissions than their fossil-based counterparts, assessing bio-oil production (Van
68 Schalkwyk et al., 2020), lignin-derived monomers and oligomers (Zeilerbauer et al., 2021), and other lignin-
69 derived products (Wenger et al., 2020). With regard to RCF technologies, five LCA studies have been conducted.
70 Bartling et al. (2021) assessed various RCF configurations using different solvents, focusing on economic and
71 GHG emission hot spots. Luo et al. (2022) analyzed the intake of yellow poplar-based residual feedstock
72 processed by the RCF biorefinery. However, both studies neglect the comparison between RCF products and their
73 alternatives. Liao et al. (2020) compared RCF lignin oil-derived products (phenolic oligomers, phenol, and
74 propylene) and their alternative counterparts (fossil oil-derived phenol, propylene, and nonylphenol), but did not
75 include a comparison between the RCF pulp and its alternative. A recent publication by Arts et al. (2023)
76 conducted a comparison between the RCF products and their alternative counterparts.

77 In the realm of sustainable technology advancement, an essential element of LCA involves evaluating the
78 performance of various alternatives (ISO 14044, 2006). This evaluation often pertains to comparing new bio-
79 based technologies or products with conventional fossil-based counterparts. Biorefineries typically generate
80 multiple products, reflecting the multifunctionality of the process and posing a specific challenge in allocating
81 environmental impacts accurately. To solve this problem it is recommended to avoid allocation by employing the
82 method of system expansion (ISO 14040, 2006). While some of the above-mentioned studies have addressed the
83 comparison aspect, the application of system expansion is missing. Navare et al. (2022) addressed the system
84 expansion of RCF's alternatives in an attributional LCA approach. However, the study did not consider the
85 prospective market dynamics and the environmental consequences of RCF products in other markets.

86 All five RCF studies applied a retrospective attributional approach that is suitable for existing technologies but
87 presents limitations when applied to the case of novel emerging technologies such as RCF. Emerging technologies
88 are typically characterized by limited data availability and an early stage of development, implying that these
89 technologies are not yet commercially available (Buyle et al., 2019; Einsiedel, 2009; Haessler et al., 2023).
90 Consequently, a prospective LCA approach becomes essential, aiming to investigate the future environmental
91 impacts of technologies still in development (Van der Giesen et al., 2020). Furthermore, a notable limitation in
92 the aforementioned studies is their emphasis on the physical flows within the system without considering the

93 environmental consequences arising from changes in demand induced by the decision to implement the
94 technology. This encompasses the impact on other markets influenced by the implementation process. While the
95 first limitation can be satisfactorily addressed by several ex-ante/prospective approaches (Arvidsson et al., 2023;
96 Van der Giesen et al., 2020), the second limitation requires the application of a consequential LCA. Consequential
97 LCA is a market-driven approach that focuses on tracing forward in time (thus, prospectively) the consequences
98 initiated by a decision, such as an increase in the demand for a product, by modeling the long-term marginal
99 changes induced by such a decision (Weidema, 2003; Weidema et al., 2018).

100 To this date, a comprehensive consequential LCA study on RCF technologies has not yet been performed. In this
101 context, the current study presents the first consequential LCA on the emerging RCF technology and its products.
102 The study aims to address the following two research questions: (i) What are the environmental consequences of
103 the RCF technology implementation, and (ii) is it environmentally desirable in comparison to the conventional
104 alternatives?

105 2 Method and materials

106 2.1 **Functional unit**

107 The studied object is the emerging RCF process that has not been commercialized yet. The RCF process produces
108 three co-products: pulp, phenolic monomers and oligomers. The lignin-first strategy considers all three RCF
109 products as equally important. Hence, all three RCF products are assessed as the determining product, separately
110 leading to three functional units. To determine the functional unit, Weidema's (2017) three-step analysis approach
111 is applied (supplementary text, goal and scope definition) to determine the functional unit of all three RCF
112 products, separately; such as the increase in demand for one kg of (i) pulp, (ii) monomers, and (iii) oligomers, at
113 the RCF-biorefinery gate 2021, produced in Belgium.

114 2.2 **System boundary**

115 Figure 1 presents the system boundary for pulp as the functional unit. The system boundary of the RCF process
116 involves three main steps such as *processing wood* (sustainable cultivation, harvesting, chipping, and drying of
117 birch as the feedstock of choice), 100 km *transportation*, and the *RCF process*. A cradle-to-gate approach is
118 applied excluding biogenic carbon uptake and emissions (see discussion in section 4.1). The system is expanded
119 to include activities affected by the increased demand for pulp, with monomers and oligomers as by-products
120 substituting fossil-based phenols and bisphenol A on the market, respectively. The choice of the determining
121 products defines which by-products are potentially substituted on the market. Figures S1&S2 in the supplementary
122 text display monomers and oligomers as the determining products. Other activities and materials remain consistent
123 regardless of the selected RCF product. The case study is based in Flanders, Belgium. Flanders has the largest
124 chemical clusters in Europe (Vanthillo et al., 2018) and a well-established pulp and paper industry (Vandereydt
125 et al., 2019). Thus, substituting the alternatives within the Belgian/Flemish chemical and paper pulp markets
126 appears reasonable.

127

128 **Figure 1.** RCF's system boundary includes sustainable wood processing steps, transportation, RCF biorefinery
 129 process, and the system expansion with the affected markets. The usage and disposal stages are excluded. Pulp is
 130 the determining product. Inflows into the system are *blue* and outflows are *red*. Emissions outflows are represented
 131 by vertical flows (*red, italic style*). Monomers and oligomers substitute their alternatives phenol and bisphenol A
 132 on the market (dashed green processes and flows).

133 2.3 Life cycle inventory

134 It is assumed that all necessary inputs for the RCF process are obtained from the Belgian market, using Belgian
 135 long-term marginal electricity and heat mixes. The current Belgian long-term marginal electricity mix from
 136 Ecoinvent 3.7.1 (consequential) is used, while a Belgian long-term marginal heat mix is created to incorporate
 137 diverse heat sources with 23.67% from natural gas and 76.32% from woodchips-based production, specifically
 138 related to the wood sector. Next, the background database 'Ecoinvent 3.7.1 (consequential)' is adjusted in
 139 Brightway 2 to ensure that all activities use the long-term marginal electricity and newly defined heat mixes (see
 140 supplementary text, Table S2).

141
 142 The activities described in supplementary text Table S1 are based on the RCF biorefinery at the technology
 143 readiness level (TRL) 4. The RCF process of this study is a modified version of Liao et al. (2020) and is
 144 downscaled to an annual capacity of 450 kilotons of wood intake per year. Input and output flows are analyzed
 145 on an hourly basis. The dried wood chips proceed to the RCF reactor after undergoing upstream processes. In the
 146 reactor, dried chipped wood is mixed with a solvent mixture of water and methanol, hydrogen, and flashed with
 147 nitrogen under high pressure to remove oxygen, facilitated by 5 wt% ruthenium on carbon (Ru/C) catalyst with a
 148 retention time of 1.5 hours. The Ru/C catalyst accounts for 2110 kg CO₂-eq./kg (Nuss and Eckelman, 2014). Other
 149 outflows are pulp and crude oil, off-gases, and a waste stream called H₂ gas bypass, consisting of gaseous
 150 (methane, hydrogen) and fluid components (methanol, methyl acetate, and water). In the separation stage,
 151 dichloromethane and water are used to separate soluble sugars and refined lignin oil from the crude oil, the latter
 152 being then separated into phenolic monomers and oligomers using n-hexane. Condensate and an aqueous rest
 153 stream (primarily water and carbohydrate derivatives) are produced as well. The ultimate output products are pulp,
 154 monomers, and oligomers. A detailed process flow diagram and mass and energy balance can be found in the
 155 study of Tschulchow et al. (2020).

156 2.4 Life cycle impact assessment method

157 In this study, the life cycle assessment method (LCIA) IPCC 2013 is applied with the impact assessment category
 158 'Global Warming Potential' with a time horizon of 100 years (GWP100) measured in carbon dioxide equivalents
 159 (kg CO₂-eq.), reported in the 5th IPCC assessment report (IPCC, 2014).

160 2.5 Contribution and sensitivity analysis

161 A contribution analysis is developed to assess the GHG hot spots of the inputs and processes to the RCF products
162 pulp, monomers, and oligomers, illustrated in Figure 1. Sensitivity analyses are performed to demonstrate the
163 impact of the main parameter variations on the GHG results assessing pulp, gaseous waste stream, and
164 transportation. The first sensitivity analysis shows how the GHG emission could change if pulp intends to
165 substitute different types of pulp products on the market, such as bleached sulfate and sulfite pulp. The second
166 sensitivity analysis examines the GHG impact of different gaseous waste stream strategies such as partial and full
167 release of the gasses into the atmosphere, and incinerate them with and without energy generation. The third
168 sensitivity analysis focused on the transportation aspect of the feedstock. By considering different transportation
169 types and distances, the GHG impact on RCF products is assessed.

170 3 Results

171 This section examines GHG emissions (CO₂-eq./kg) and the consequences associated with the implementation of
172 the RCF-biorefinery and its lignin valorization strategy. Pulp, monomers, and oligomers exhibit GHG emissions
173 of -0.25, 3.65, and 5.24 kg CO₂-eq./kg, respectively. In comparison, unbleached sulfate pulp, fossil oil-based
174 phenol and bisphenol A generate GHG emissions of -0.425, 2.55, and 3.41 kg CO₂-eq./kg, respectively. These
175 results will serve as a reference for the upcoming assessments.

176 3.1 Contribution analysis

177 Figure 2 presents the contributions of RCF inputs/outputs to the net GHG emissions of 1 kg of pulp, monomers,
178 and oligomers. Processing wood and transportation are relatively low in terms of the overall GHG emissions of
179 the target products. Materials employed in the RCF process, namely methanol, hydrogen, Ru/C catalyst, hexane,
180 and dichloromethane, contribute collectively 0.14, 0.86, and 1.43 kg CO₂-eq./kg to the net GHG emissions of
181 pulp, monomers, and oligomers, respectively. Despite the significant GHG emissions associated with ruthenium
182 production, amounting to 2110 kg CO₂-eq./kg (Nuss and Eckelman, 2014), Ru/C catalyst has a relatively minor
183 impact on overall GHG emissions. It contributes only 0.03, 0.18, and 0.3 kg CO₂-eq./kg to pulp, monomers, and
184 oligomers, respectively. This is attributed to the assumed reusability of the Ru/C catalyst over four years, resulting
185 in a reduction in GHG emissions per produced unit. Interestingly, hexane decreases the net GHG emissions of the
186 end products. A marginal amount of electricity is generated contributing positively to all RCF products. Methane
187 (CH₄) inherent in the gaseous waste stream has a substantial negative GHG contribution, with 29.7 kg CO₂-eq./kg
188 (IPCC, 2014), leading to contributions of 0.24, 1.44, and 2.40 kg CO₂-eq./kg to the net GHG emissions of pulp,
189 monomers, and oligomers, respectively.

190 The greatest contributions to GHG emissions in RCF products stem from dependent by-products. For pulp (Figure
191 2a), monomers and oligomers are the dependent by-products, substituting their respective alternatives on the
192 market, namely phenol and bisphenol A. The production of 1 kg of pulp comes with 0.164 kg of monomers and
193 0.098 kg of oligomers, which substitute equivalent amounts of phenols and bisphenol A on the market. This
194 substitution yields a credit of -0.418 kg CO₂-eq./kg for phenols and -0.335 kg CO₂-eq./kg for bisphenol A,
195 effectively reducing the GHG emissions associated with pulp production. Consequently, both monomers and
196 oligomers contribute positively to the overall GHG emission reduction of pulp.

197 When monomers and oligomers serve as the determining products (Figure 2b&c), two opposing effects on net
198 GHG emissions can be observed. Firstly, the by-product "oligomers" (monomers) provides a credit of -2.05 (-
199 4.26) kg CO₂-eq./kg to the determining product "monomers" (oligomers). Secondly, the by-product "pulp"
200 increases the net GHG emissions of monomers and oligomers by 2.60 and 4.33 kg CO₂-eq./kg, respectively. The
201 production of pulp substitutes unbleached sulfate pulp on the market, which typically exhibits net negative GHG
202 emissions of -0.426 kg CO₂-eq./kg. Consequently, the production of pulp yields a reverse GHG emission effect
203 on the pulp, benefiting the climate.

204

205 **Figure 2.** Contribution analyses: RCF (a) pulp (*green*), (b) monomers (*blue*), and (c) oligomers (*yellow*) are
 206 assessed separately as the determining products. Activities/inputs remain the same for all three determining
 207 products. Only by-products change (*last two rows*). For each determining product, two by-products are
 208 considered: for pulp (a); monomers and oligomers, for monomers (b); pulp and oligomers, and for oligomers (c);
 209 pulp and monomers.

210 3.2 Sensitivity analysis

211 3.2.1 RCF pulp

212 This section analyses how sensitive the GHG outcomes are if RCF pulp would hypothetically substitute different
 213 pulp products on the pulp market. Figure 3 illustrates three pulp products: unbleached sulfate pulp (base case),
 214 bleached sulfate, and sulfite pulp. Substituting unbleached sulfate pulp on the pulp market (-1.49 kg CO₂-eq./kg)
 215 negatively affects the GHG emissions of monomers (3.65 kg CO₂-eq./kg) and oligomers (5.24 kg CO₂-eq./kg).
 216 This is due to the fact that the pulp substitutes a climate-beneficial product on the market, as discussed in section
 217 3.1. On the other hand, bleached sulfate pulp (0.23 kg CO₂-eq./kg) reduces the GHG emissions of monomers and
 218 oligomers by up to 4.01 and 6.69 kg CO₂-eq./kg, respectively. A similar outcome is observed for bleached sulfite
 219 pulp (0.30 kg CO₂-eq./kg) with a potential GHG emission reduction of 4.46 and 7.43 kg CO₂-eq./kg, respectively.
 220 Therefore, targeting bleached sulfate and sulfite pulp could offer notable GHG emission reductions.

221 At this point, bleached sulfite and sulfate pulp are considered from a hypothetical point of view. One argument is
 222 that pulp does not have same the functionality as bleached sulfite and sulfate pulp. Although processes are similar,
 223 additional chlorine bleaching processes are necessary (Bajpai, 2018). Nevertheless, the results encourage further
 224 investigation of different pulps supported by the hypothesis that pulp requires a less stringent bleaching step for
 225 such applications due to the stabilizing hydrogenation reactions in RCF and the avoided base-catalyzed
 226 polymerization reactions compared to sulfate pulps (Liao et al., 2020).

227

228 **Figure 3.** Comparative GHG emission analysis: RCF pulp substituting three alternative products – unbleached
 229 sulfate pulp (base case), bleached sulfate, and sulfite pulp – on the pulp market.

230 3.2.2 *Gaseous waste stream treatment*

231 In this section, four scenarios of how to treat the gaseous waste stream are examined, as highlighted in Figure 4
 232 and supplementary text, Table S3. In the base case scenario, RCF process of Tschulchow et al. (2020) releases the
 233 gaseous waste stream, in which hydrogen is not considered as a direct GHG, only methane. In the second scenario,
 234 hydrogen is factored with 11 kg CO₂-eq./kg (Warwick et al., 2022). Hydrogen is regarded as an indirect GHG,
 235 not possessing a warming effect on its own but participating in atmospheric chemical reactions that influence the
 236 lifespan and concentrations of other GHGs (Sand et al., 2023). It is evident that accounting for hydrogen leads to
 237 an increase in GHG emissions compared to the base case scenario. Thirdly, the gasses are subjected to flaring.
 238 According to Muller and Muller (2017), flaring 1 kg of methane emits 2.75 kg of CO₂, thereby reducing the
 239 methane's impact by nearly 11-fold. Flaring of hydrogen is assumed to have no GHG emissions and thus
 240 effectively mitigates the GHG emissions of all RCF products, resulting in lower emissions compared to their
 241 current market alternatives. Building on the flaring approach, the fourth scenario assumes the integration of a
 242 combined (cooling) heating and power plant (C(C)HP). Assuming an overall energy efficiency of 85% (Liao et
 243 al., 2020), the C(C)HP is anticipated to generate an additional 12 914 kWh of energy, comprising 4 386 kWh of
 244 electricity and 30704 MJ of heating and cooling energy (see supplementary text, Table S4). Consequently, the
 245 C(C)HP would further reduce GHG emissions, making it the most favorable option. It's worth noting that
 246 implementing a C(C)HP involves adding a new unit and, consequently, additional costs. Alternatively, the gaseous
 247 waste stream can be directed to an external incineration facility. In summary, the preferable choices are either
 248 flaring or C(C)HP, as opposed to releasing the gases into the atmosphere.

249

250 **Figure 4.** Scenario analysis: (1) Methane and hydrogen are emitted into the atmosphere (Release); (2) only
 251 methane is emitted (Base case), (3) gasses are incinerated (Flaring), and (4) and energy is generated in the C(C)HP
 252 unit. All RCF products are compared to their alternatives on the market, represented by the same color.

253 3.2.3 Transportation types and distances

254 In this study, RCF biorefinery is located in Flanders, Belgium. Wood is assumed to be sourced from Flemish
 255 forests with an average transportation distance of 100 km. However, given a relatively low forest coverage of 11%
 256 (Vandekerkhove, 2013) and a high wood utilization rate of 98.7% (Forest Europe and UNECE and FAO, 2020),
 257 it raises questions about whether the Flemish wood suppliers could provide the demanded 450 kilotons feedstock
 258 per year. Therefore, considering imports from wood-abundant countries seems reasonable. Table 1 presents the
 259 GHG impact of transportation on 1 kg of pulp. The same trend is observed for the transportation of monomers and
 260 oligomers. Different transportation types such as truckload (> 32 metric tons), inland waterways (barge), and
 261 sea container shipping are compared. The comparison shows that 100 km of truck transport is approximately
 262 equivalent to 200 km of inland waterway shipping or 1000 km of sea container shipping. Thus, expanding the
 263 supplier distance to 1000 km using different transportation types would not significantly affect the GHG emissions
 264 of pulp but would enhance feedstock availability for potential RCF biorefineries. In comparison to the base case
 265 scenario of 100 km, the inland waterway could expand the importing distance by 200 km without increasing the
 266 GHG emissions. Neighboring wood-abundant countries such as Germany and France with production capacities
 267 around of 70 and 50 million m³ roundwood under bark could be reached. With sea container shipping (1000 km),
 268 Sweden and Finland could serve as suppliers producing 75 and 70 million m³ roundwood per year, respectively.
 269 Hence, a location in Flanders can potentially receive its wood supply from 50% of the total European roundwood
 270 production without increasing the GHG emissions. These findings supportively lead to the conclusion that from
 271 a GHG emission point of view, RCF biorefinery should be closely located to an (international) waterway rather
 272 than being closer to the forest-rich region in Flanders.

273

Table 1. GHG emission comparison based on transportation type and distance (km).

	Truck	Inland waterways	Sea, containership
kg CO ₂ -eq./tkm	0.088	0.046	0.009
kg CO ₂ -eq. per x distance contributing to pulp GHG emissions			
100 km	0.034	0.018	0.004
200 km	0.068	0.035	0.007
500 km	0.171	0.088	0.018
1000 km	0.342	0.176	0.037

274 3.3 RCF process configuration

275 To gain a comprehensive understanding of the GHG emissions related to the "lignin-first" RCF technology, it is
276 important to consider different configurations of the RCF technology. This expanded focus enables a thorough
277 analysis of the consequences and GHG emission implications of various lignin-first RCF technologies. Figure 5
278 illustrates the reference process of the study (RCF) and its extended version (RCF_extension) described in Liao
279 et al. (2020) under a 450 kilotons feedstock (birch) intake per year. The reference process of the study (RCF)
280 focuses on the production of pulp, phenolic monomers and oligomers, consisting of a RCF reactor and separation
281 unit. The RCF_extension enhances the RCF process of this study by hydroprocessing and dealkylation/distillation
282 units to further convert phenolic monomers into phenols and propylene. Unlike the RCF process, the
283 RCF_extension is distinguished by the inclusion of a combined (cooling) heating and power (C(C)HP) unit,
284 rendering it entirely self-sustaining in terms of energy. Both processes are compared to their alternative products
285 that are aimed to be substituted on their markets. The comparison analysis shows that RCF_extension has lower
286 GHG emissions than the RCF process of this study. The RCF extension by meaning is further expanded to
287 processes to further utilize the biomass and optimize the process. A certain fraction of monomers is used to
288 produce bio-based propylene potentially substituting fossil-based propylene on the market. Propylene has lower
289 GHG emissions than phenols. Hence, the positive impact of the substitution effect decreases which in turn
290 increases the GHG emissions of the RCF_extension. This effect is further enforced by the biomass loss in the
291 further processing stages lowering the lignin-derived products-to-wood intake from 16.23% to 12.5%.
292 Consequently, the lower amount of lignin oil-based mass substitutes fewer low-GHG emission-based products on
293 the market. Moreover, the additional processing steps increase the energy consumption of the RCF process. On
294 the other hand, RCF extension includes a C(C)HP unit incinerating the highly polluting gaseous waste stream
295 including methane. By doing that, RCF_extension is not only self-sustained but also generates a net energy
296 outcome of 15104 kWh (3951 kg CO₂-eq. savings/hour) that can be fed into the energy grid. To put that into
297 relation, RCF process does not have a C(C)HP unit and needs an external energy intake, leading to an energy
298 consumption of 18382 kWh (1977 kg CO₂-eq./hour) which also causes the release of 278.36 kg methane per hour,
299 inherent in the gaseous waste stream. Overall, for the RCF_extension the incineration of gaseous waste stream
300 along with a net energy generation outweighs the impacts of the above-mentioned points resulting from the
301 modification. This outcome corresponds with the finding in section 3.2.2, to incinerate the gaseous waste and
302 consequently highly suggests considering an incineration unit such as C(C)HP for the RCF process of this study.

303

304 **Figure 5.** Comparative analysis between two different RCF configurations; RCF (base case) and RCF_extension,
 305 a further development of the RCF base case. All RCF products are compared with their alternative products that
 306 are aimed to be substituted on the market, represented by the same color.

307 4 Discussion and limitations

308 **4.1 Biogenic carbon and the cradle-to-gate approach**

309 Dealing with biomass feedstocks in LCA's, the literature suggests considering biogenic carbon by using the '-
 310 1/+1' approach under cradle-to-grave approach (Garcia and Freire, 2014). Biogenic carbon is withdrawn
 311 (sequestered) from the atmosphere in the growth process of plants and is released back to it in the later stage of
 312 decomposition. Hence, biogenic carbon flows are considered as neutral. To guarantee a proper comparison
 313 between the novel RCF products and the alternatives, this paper considers a cradle-to-gate approach excluding
 314 biogenic carbon flows contradicting the above-mentioned '-1/+1' approach. This is justified for the following
 315 reasons. RCF products and their alternative products are intermediate products from which multiple end products
 316 can be produced. This in turn means that ultimate use and end-of-life stages cannot be defined which challenges
 317 the definition of the biogenic carbon lifetime that is embedded in the RCF products (Arts et al., 2023). Particularly
 318 for RCF products, the developers focus on a wide application range rather than on a single end-use product.
 319 Another challenge arises if the lifetime of the biogenic carbon in the products is not sufficiently long with respect
 320 to the rotation time of the trees (see section 4.2) complicating the evaluation of the GHG emissions of RCF process
 321 parameters on the LCA (Arts et al., 2023).

322 **4.2 The lifetime of the products**

323 While this paper did not consider biogenic carbon, understanding the timing implications of its uptake and release
 324 into the atmosphere is crucial. In theory, a unit of carbon is absorbed from the atmosphere and released back at
 325 the end of its life stage. However, this theoretical approach doesn't always hold true. Carbon neutrality is achieved
 326 only if the time between capturing and releasing carbon aligns with the timing of having an identical newly grown
 327 feedstock (e.g. an average tree rotation time of 60 years) (Nabuurs et al., 2014). Depending on the chosen end
 328 product, the product's lifespan may significantly deviate, impacting carbon neutrality.

329 RCF pulp is intended to substitute unbleached sulfate pulp, which is commonly used in paper and packaging
330 products. However, these products generally have short lifespans and are often disposed of, usually by
331 incineration. As a result, GHG emissions that were initially sequestered in the woody biomass are reemitted into
332 the atmosphere after a brief life cycle. While paper recycling can extend the lifespan, the effectiveness of recycling
333 is limited as each iteration leads to shorter fibers and weaker inter-fiber bonding, diminishing the functionality of
334 the recycled paper (Yang and Berglund, 2020).

335 Lignin-derived monomers and oligomers aim to substitute phenols and bisphenol A's derived from fossil oil.
336 These lignin-derived compounds offer a wide range of applications in various processed products. Liao et al.
337 (2020) showed that monomers and oligomers can be employed to produce propylene and printing ink,
338 respectively. Printing ink is incinerated along with paper products that are usually disposed of shortly after
339 production. Propylene serves as a fundamental component for various end products. By far, the greatest
340 application is polypropylene plastic ranging from short to long lifespans. Currently, there is an increasing research
341 effort being done on plastic recycling methods (Schyns and Shaver, 2021) with the potential to expand the lifespan
342 of plastic by multiple times depending on the number of recycling cycles. Propylene oxide, another derivative of
343 propylene, can be utilized to create durable products such as furniture and mechanical parts (Hocking, 2005).
344 Zhang et al. (2022) explored the potential of polypropylene fibers in cement to enhance functionality and reduce
345 cement usage. The application of propylene in the construction field could substantially increase its lifespan (e.g.
346 up to 100 years for concrete).

347 The potential lifespan of RCF end products can have a broad range. For some of the products, the biogenic carbon
348 life cycle is shorter than the rotation time of the feedstock. In this case, the product cannot be considered carbon
349 neutral. Hence, when developing RCF processes, careful consideration should be given to the life cycle of the
350 potential end products as this can contribute to further improvement of RCF's environmental performance.

351 **4.3 (In-)direct land-use change**

352 This study does not consider the potential impacts of (in-)direct land-use change, which can be significant when
353 evaluating wood-based biorefineries like the RCF process. Arneth et al. (2017) have argued that GHG emissions
354 resulting from land-use change have been underestimated in existing literature, and unsustainable wood harvesting
355 practices can lead to a reduction in carbon density. Therefore, excluding land-use change from the analysis can
356 lead to misleading conclusions. In this study, Belgium is the location of choice, where forest preservation and
357 protection are mandatory. Sustainable forest management practices, including thinning, are commonly employed
358 in Belgium to promote forest health and tree growth (Perin et al., 2018). Thus, it can be cautiously assumed that
359 (in-)direct land-use changes are limited in Belgium. However, as mentioned in the previous section 3.2.3, it is
360 highly unlikely that the Belgian forest alone can supply an additional 450 kilotons/year of wood, necessitating
361 wood imports. While other European countries may also practice sustainable forest management, it cannot be
362 ruled out that wood could originate from regions with loose or unenforced forest protection regulations, potentially
363 resulting in clear-cutting or illegal deforestation and subsequent land-use changes. However, assessing the precise
364 impact of such land-use and land-cover changes is challenging and considered highly uncertain (Arneth et al.,
365 2017).

366 Considering that wood is traded globally, the effect of increased demand for wood can lead to (in-)direct land-use
367 change regardless of the specific harvested region (Pizzol and Scotti, 2017). Historical trends show a steady
368 increase in wood demand over time accompanied by rising wood prices (European Commission, 2020). This
369 implies that additional demand for RCF will prompt market participants to seek alternative sources of supply.
370 This process continues until the last actor in the market obtains its supply from regions with lax regulations, as
371 mentioned earlier. Therefore, it is important to acknowledge that even if additional RCF demand is met using
372 sustainable wood from Europe, it can still contribute to deforestation in other parts of the world. In this case, a
373 shift towards wood-like feedstocks could be beneficial. To partially mitigate the impact of the (in-)direct land use
374 change, RCF biorefinery is able to process agricultural residues (Ebikade et al., 2020) and post-consumer wood-
375 waste (Van den Bossche et al., 2022).

376 4.4 Substitution effect

377 Numerous RCF products and their potential to substitute several alternatives have been discussed in this study. It
378 highlights that understanding the substitution effect is crucial for reducing GHG emissions of RCF products.
379 However, substitution can be also a source of uncertainty. The extent of substitution depends on the functional
380 equivalence between the novel RCF products and their alternatives, which is determined by their chemical and
381 structural characteristics. Regarding pulp, its functional equivalence to unbleached sulfate pulp is determined by
382 the purity and long fibers of the product, which are essential for paper and cupboard production (Yang and
383 Berglund, 2020). For RCF monomers and oligomers, chemical equivalence plays a pivotal role. While the study
384 conducted by Van Aelst et al. (2021) indicated a suitable equivalence of oligomers to bisphenol A in epoxy resins,
385 the functional equivalence of pulp and monomers relies on the expertise of the RCF developers. Therefore, more
386 research on the functional equivalence of the RCF products is required.

387 4.5 Technological uncertainty

388 The study showed that RCF products are outperformed by their alternatives. However, the comparison is made
389 between the emerging RCF technology and its mature commercialized competitors consequently holding
390 uncertainty about the comparability of the study. Technological uncertainties associated with the RCF process
391 and its products arise from their current lab-pilot stage (TRL 3-5). Until reaching the commercial stage (TRL 9),
392 the emerging stage of RCF introduces the possibility of changes in chemical, technological, and thermodynamic
393 conditions. Factors like economies of scale and environmental synergies that may emerge in scaled-up facilities
394 are not considered and cannot reflect the finite outcome at the commercial stage. In a recent study, Cooreman et
395 al. (2023) tested three different scaled RCF reactors (100 ml, 2l, and 50l) showing limited impact on the product
396 formation and their qualities. This can be seen as a promising step towards higher scalability. Despite substantial
397 research efforts in the recent years, several technical upscaling challenges remain. Particularly, high operating
398 pressure associated with the usage of hydrogen and flammable solvents and the reactor design remain unresolved
399 (Cooreman et al., 2020). Consequently, the overall impact of upscaling on GHG results remains uncertain. In
400 contrast, the alternative technologies are commercialized and have undergone extensive R&D, offering efficiency
401 advantages at large scales. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that current alternatives hold a technological advantage
402 over emerging technologies which are also reflected in their environmental benefits. In turn, that also means that
403 the RCF process holds a technological disadvantage due to its low TRL but could potentially change positively
404 with increasing maturity. Scaling up and learning effects can help overcome the limitations of emerging
405 technologies. To address the challenges of scaling up and potential learning effects in early-stage technologies,
406 techniques, as demonstrated by Pizzol et al. (2021), can account for the non-linearity and technological maturity
407 of such activities. Nevertheless, the efficiency gains and learning effects resulting from multiple factory
408 implementations (TRL 9+) have not been explored yet and should be considered in future research.

409 4.6 Modeling uncertainty

410 To address the technological uncertainties mentioned above, it is crucial to adopt an appropriate LCA modeling
411 approach. Existing ex-ante LCA methodologies predominantly focus on the technology itself, using techniques
412 such as scaling up and learning curves. What is overlooked is the background system, which remains in its current
413 state. This results in a temporal mismatch between the foreground (technology) and background systems
414 (Arvidsson et al., 2018; Mendoza Beltran et al., 2018). This discrepancy becomes particularly evident when
415 practitioners utilize attributional-based databases with average data regarding the market supply mixes. This
416 problem can be solved by using prospective databases as proposed by Sacchi et al. (2022), which has already led
417 to its application by projecting future electricity scenarios (background system) for lithium-ion batteries (Šimaitis
418 et al., 2023).

419 In this study, the use of a consequential approach in modeling both the background and the foreground system
420 allows to reduce technological uncertainties associated with the prospective and ex-ante assessments. In fact, the
421 marginal mixes used in the model take into account the technological development as only modern, unconstrained

422 technologies with the capacity to increase production are included in this mix (e.g. Belgian electricity mix), thus
423 better reflecting the future conditions in which the technology will operate compared to the use of average supply
424 mixes.

425 5 Conclusion

426 This study conducted the first consequential LCA on the 'lignin-first' RCF process and its products (pulp, phenolic
427 monomers, and oligomers) comparing them to their alternative counterparts (unbleached sulfate pulp, phenol, and
428 bisphenol A). The objective was to analyze the environmental consequences of implementing the RCF process
429 and determine its environmental desirability compared to conventional alternatives.

430 The assessment revealed that, without optimization of the design, RCF products have higher GHG emissions than
431 their current alternatives. Notably, RCF by-products and the gaseous waste stream were identified as the major
432 contributors to the GHG emissions of the RCF process. The study proposed optimization strategies, emphasizing
433 product substitution for high-polluting alternatives and integrating a combined heat and power unit to incinerate
434 the gaseous waste stream. Transportation analysis indicated that waterway-based transport could expand feedstock
435 availability in wood-abundant countries (e.g. Germany, France, Sweden, and Finland) without increasing GHG
436 emissions. That implies that wood import is reasonable and that access to waterways is competitive to land-based
437 locations in forest-rich environments.

438 The study excluded biogenic carbon to ensure comparability between RCF products and alternatives, considering
439 the intermediate nature of the products without a defined lifespan, complicating carbon release timing
440 identification. Next, (in-)direct land use change was discussed, emphasizing the potential negative GHG emission
441 impacts of wood demand, regardless of the origin of the wood sources. Uncertainty sources were identified as the
442 substitution effect and technological immaturity. Clear choices in process development and product selection were
443 recommended for addressing substitution effect uncertainty, while scaling up the process and incorporating
444 learning effects were advised for technological uncertainty. Aligning the foreground and background systems in
445 a prospective manner was suggested to reduce model-associated uncertainty.

446 This study promotes the consequential LCA approach for its valuable insights into how future production and use
447 of RCF products can influence the environmental performance. It shows the consequences of the impacts beyond
448 the RCF products such as the consequences on other actors on the market. In conclusion, the consequential LCA
449 approach proves valuable for evaluating the environmental impacts of RCF implementation and guiding
450 technology developers toward environmentally friendly product pathways.

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